

Capacity building, trainings, and policy recommendations - Initial

D5.3

CiROCCO

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

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Consortium

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CD	Capacity Development
GEO	Group of Earth Observations
CD-WG	Capacity Development Working Group
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
Mxx	Month Number
PM	Particulate Matter
EWS	Early Warning System
Dx.x	Deliverable Number
WP(x)	Work Package(Number)
EO	Earth Observation
ICT	Information and communications technology
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
DDS	Desert Dust Storm
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature

Executive Summary

H1 Goal / Objectives

This Deliverable (D5.3, initial) sets out the capacity-building guidelines to be followed by the four (4) CiROCCO pilot studies throughout the project. It addresses the general Capacity Development (CD) principles, outlines the fit-for-purpose guidelines for each of the 4 pilots -co-designed with the pilot leaders (and trainers) and stakeholders- and incorporates the plan for knowledge transfer and capacity building in the frame of the project. It also reports the first Liaison activities of CiROCCO with decision-makers, at local, national and European levels towards supporting policy initiatives.

The ultimate goal of Task 5.2, which drives the activities described in this deliverable, is to launch outreach training and capacity-building activities among the wider public to enable, in particular, stakeholders, to raise awareness, educate and encourage to widely use/adopt the CiROCCO technical solution/developed solutions, aiming for improved geographical coverage.

H2 Methodology

The work performed within Task 5.2 and described in D5.3 (initial) entails the exploration of the good practices for designing, implementing, and evaluating capacity development interventions reported by the Group of Earth Observations (GEO) [1]. Additional information stemming from the United Nations Development Group acts as supporting information to frame the general guidelines for the CiROCCO CD strategy [2].

In the frame of the co-design and co-development of CD strategy and interventions, (virtual) meetings with pilot leaders have been performed, to identify pilot particularities. Beyond the ‘trainers view’, the stakeholders’ input and preferences are gathered, through the use of targeted questions posed during each pilot workshop. The process of feedback from both types of interactions will co-define and enrich the whole CD process that each pilot should follow.

H3 Outcomes / Conclusions

This Deliverable is intended to serve as guidance in the CD activities of each pilot of the Project towards the adoption and sustainability of the products in the four pilot studies. Pilot leaders and other trainers are strongly encouraged to look back at this Deliverable during their preparatory and implementation activities in the frame of CD, considering at the same time that upcoming workshops with stakeholders may add more supportive information for their CD interventions. Future works relevant to CD planning and activities, as well as monitoring and evaluation processes and outputs, will contribute to enriching the existing material, which will be reported as D5.4 (final).

Key outcomes/conclusions

Aspects related to the capacity development in the frame of the CiROCCO Project are addressed in this Deliverable (initial phase). Overall, D5.3 serves as a basis to plan, implement, monitor, and evaluate the necessary knowledge transfer and capacity building for each pilot area/ case.

Capacity development is governed by 4 basic principles (Section 2), is based on 4 different types of intervention tools, and is composed of 3 different phases, which form the CiROCCO knowledge transfer plan (Section 3).

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Description

The description of this deliverable as mentioned in the Grant Agreement (GA) is as follows: “Capacity building, trainings and policy recommendations (NOA) [M10, M35]: Initial (A) version, including the guidelines and training templates, and final (B) version presenting the implemented capacity building activities and training material, as well as the policy recommendations.”

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

A significant part of this document is devoted to providing CD guidelines, which is the main objective of this deliverable. Specific interventions (e.g. training options and tools) will be decided at a later stage, once each pilot study has matured and stakeholders have provided their feedback. Such definitions will impose the necessary training materials.

1.3. Intended Audience

The dissemination level of this document is public, therefore, apart from its dissemination internally within the project, it will also be published online on the project website. The plan set out in this document will govern the actions of CiROCCO pilot partners throughout the CD duration. It is therefore important that all partners have access to it and the possibility to consult it at all times. Below, the intended audience is listed in alphabetic order:

1. CD leaders of similar projects
2. CiROCCO consortium
3. European Commission
4. GEO CD Group
5. Pilot leaders and other trainers
6. Stakeholders interested to uptake of the CiROCCO pilot products.

1.4. Deliverable Structure and its Relation with Other Work Packages/Deliverables

Section 2 describes the overall approach for developing the CD strategy for CiROCCO and the four (4) underlying principles it will be based on. Section 3 provides the four (4) main tools for developing the CD initiatives, according to the particularities of each pilot study. Section 4 provides an insight into the CD interventions, in terms of design, implementation, and evaluation for each case study of CiROCCO. Section 5 outlines the objectives of the Liaison strategy of CiROCCO and the relevant realized activities. Section 6 provides the main conclusions from the current status of Task 5.2, while Section 7 cites the references utilized to build this document.

Task 5.2 can benefit from the end-user needs analysis and assessment performed in the frame of Task 2.1. It has also benefited from WP4 by interacting with each pilot leader. WP3 is expected to provide human resources to support the CD/training activities. Inversely, Task 5.2 provides material to support the dedicated workshops for the stakeholder communities in each pilot area. D5.3 (initial and final version) will additionally stand as a guidebook for the CD plans and activities performed in the frame of pilots.

2. Approach and principles of CD for CiROCCO

CiROCCO’s interpretation of CD is based on the latest “User Guide on Good Practices for designing, implementing, and evaluating capacity development interventions” produced by the relevant working group (CD-WG) of GEO (Dec. 2022) [1]. GEO has recognized CD as a main aim of the group on a global scale. The greatest impact on human well-being comes when nations and organizations are enabled to create their information so that policy actors can make use of it. The net result is trusted information that can quickly be turned into decisions. Co-creation has been identified as the main principle of CD, together with providing conceptual support to the design, development, implementation, and evaluation of capacity development activities at various levels of intervention. The overarching goal of the CD-WG of GEO is to build individual, organisational, and institutional capacity and capabilities.

The underlying principles of the CD efforts in the frame of CiROCCO are shortly given in Figure 1 and described in the next subsections. It should be noted that stakeholders’ engagement and sustainability belong to the CD principles but are not analysed here, as they belong to other tasks of CiROCCO, which are in collaboration with T5.2 so that they incorporate CD aspects where and when necessary.

Figure 1: CiROCCO’s Principles for Capacity Development (CD) (adapted from the GEO capacity development strategy).

2.1. Leveraging existing capacities

CD interventions call on the capacities and capabilities that already exist within the audience groups, especially those that are or will be accessible through the project consortium. Existing competencies are explored through the interaction with stakeholders during the four workshops organized in the frame of each pilot. Desired competencies are dictated by each pilot, in terms of defining requirements to adopt the developed solutions. Bridging the gap between existing and desired competencies is a main principle of the CD procedure.

2.2. Demand-driven and impact-oriented

In the general frame of CiROCCO, the demand is the development of an atmospheric monitoring system and network in remote, desert/sandy, and under-sampled areas. In addition, CD interventions aim at engaging stakeholders with the activities of each pilot and train them to adopt the developed solutions and integrate them into their existing monitoring systems or developed solutions to tackle dust intrusions, air pollution, fires, land degradation etc.

2.3. Co-design, co-creation, co-development

Co-creation of CD efforts where supply and demand come together -rather than one-way provision from CiROCCO to stakeholders- is a methodology that supports the holistic approach of developing and strengthening knowledge and expertise based on the existing capabilities of the individuals, leaders, organizations, and societies. The latter, together with understanding end-user needs, necessitates a co-creation approach.

To this end, potential stakeholders have been engaged with the CD procedure since the first steps of the CiROCCO project, contacted to communicate their existing capacities and user needs concerning atmospheric monitoring and dust intrusion prediction in desert-impacted and/or under-sampled areas.

2.4. Fit-for-purpose approach

A “fit-for-purpose” or “good-fit” approach to strengthen the end-user(s) of the product(s) of each pilot requires a clear understanding of the specific focus of each case study/pilot and the needs of the different audiences per pilot and pilot area. The “uniqueness” and particularities of each ‘pilot system’ does not allow a “one-size-fits-all” development process for designing CD interventions in the frame of CiROCCO. The capacity of the Organization(s)/representative(s) to take up the data product(s) of each pilot case for decision-making will vary. Hence, each of the identified audiences is already in contact with the pilot leaders towards identifying needs and CD interventions.

3. Tools to create impactful CD interventions – Capacity building plan

This section provides the four main tools for developing the CD initiative for CiROCCO (Figure 2). Each tool is defined and then shaped according to the particularities of the project. These tools are the basis of the knowledge transfer and capacity building plan, which is also given in this section. This plan will be continuously updated, to actively engage and attract the target groups and stakeholders of the CiROCCO project.

Figure 2: CiROCCO's tools to support Capacity Development (CD) (adapted from the GEO capacity development strategy).

3.1. Preparation – Engagement with key players

As a first step, a good understanding of the situation (current situation, challenges, key actors, and factors at play, etc.) is necessary. Beyond homework on the overall plan of each pilot case, meetings with the key players took place in advance, in a non-physical manner. More specifically, in the frame of capacity development planning for each pilot, engagement events with each pilot leader were arranged and took place (Table 1).

Specific questions were raised and discussed during these preparative events, which can be found in Table 2.

It should be noted that key players declared no need for training templates at this phase, given that CD interventions will be decided in due course.

Table 1: Engagement activity with key players for the CD activities in the frame of CiROCCO

No#	Key player(s)	Pilot#	Date	Format
1	UCY (Petros Mouzourides)	2 (Cyprus)	21/11/23	Online meeting
2	CEDARE (Hesham M. El-Askary, Omar Elbadawy)	1 (Egypt)	24/11/23	Online meeting
3	VSUME (Ivana Vasic)	3 (Serbia)	28/11/23	Online meeting
4	CSIC (Francisco Javier Alcalá García, Raúl Segura Tejada)	4 (Spain)	29/11/23	E-mail

Table 2: Feedback by key players of each CiROCCO pilot, for the development of the fit-for-purpose CD plan.

No.	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4
Which is the product/tool/service outcome(s)?	1. Atmospheric monitoring network covering the Benban solar farm (Egypt). 2. Optimization of solar energy potential algorithm for the area.	1. Early Warning System (EWS; mobile app and/or portal) for dust intrusions over the broader area of Idalion Municipality (Cyprus). 2. Atmospheric monitoring network covering the municipality.	1. Atmospheric monitoring network over Deliblato sands (Serbia). 2. Optimization of the fire protection mechanism.	1. Atmospheric monitoring network covering the Balsablanca and Llano de los Juanes (Spain) experimental sites. 2. Optimizing ecosystem and groundwater quality predictions.
The available budget for capacity-building activities.		Trainees adopting solutions are CIROCCO partners; €1000 provision for extra training.		
Who will be the trainer?	CEDARE, NOA	UCY	VSUME	CSIC
Who will be trained/ adopt the developed solution(s)?	Solar investors, M. of Electricity, Renewable energy authorities.	Idalion Municipality, MOL Ministry.	Provincial authorities.	CSIC, local authorities.
What is the envisioned outcome (and impact) of the CD process?	Adoption of the optimized SOLEA system.	1. Broad use of the DSS, 2. Integration of the sensor network in the national	Sustain the established monitoring network to support the 2	Identify the impact of atmospheric dust on ecosystems

		atmospheric monitoring network.	cities and fire prevention for Deliblato sands.	and groundwater quality.
Other comments	The usefulness of EO (ground measurements) for the stakeholders of the pilot area is not clear so far. CiROCCO aims to raise awareness, through educational events, so that EOs are integrated into their systems of exploiting solar energy.	Stakeholders (trainees) are CiROCCO partners, so CD activities to support the use and sustainability of the new sensor network will benefit from this particularity.	Deliblato area is not a desert/impacted by desert dust intrusions. Nevertheless, an air pollution monitoring network could be an added value to the protection of the area against fires.	The Spanish areas are located in heavily exploited aquifers impacted by desert dust intrusions. An air pollution monitoring network could serve as an EWS to forecast the impact on groundwater quality.

3.2. Interaction with Stakeholders

At the first phase of the project, four (4) stakeholder workshops have been designed, one for each pilot. The ones for Pilots 2 and 3 are already completed (Nov-Dec 2023) in Cyprus and Serbia, respectively. Pilot 1 will be held in Egypt at the beginning of 2024, while the one for Pilot 4 will be organized at a later stage. The objectives of these workshops are the following:

- Engagement with the broader stakeholder community/ target audiences for each pilot case and area.
- Raise awareness of the pilot planning and expected outcomes.
- Identification of specific/targeted user needs, relevant to the pilot case/product/area.
- Exploration of existing capabilities and capacities to address the particular environmental issue each pilot deals with/involves.
- Collection of information on the desired CD interventions and modalities

Three means of interaction between the key players (Sect. 3.1) and stakeholders for each pilot have been selected: open discussion, input in paper format and an online survey. The feedback is/will be gathered and processed according to the aforementioned objectives.

The questions (to be) hosted in the two types of forms, directly dedicated to CD, can be found below.

Questions (to be) handed out and answered in paper format:

1. How important do you consider the problem of dust intrusions (and/or air pollution and/or fire hazard) (on energy security and/or water bodies quality) in your area and why (frequency, severity etc.)?
2. Which stakeholder groups do you hold as key actors accountable for dealing with the problem of desert dust events/ Environmental Restoration Support?

3. Can you identify any gaps in the current (local and/or National and/or European scale) regulation for dust storms, air pollution or fire hazards and the affected sectors (e.g., environment, health, solar energy, water provision)?
4. What is the capacity of your organization to tackle the problem of dust events (and the subsequent effect on energy, environment, water, and health) and/or air pollution and/or fire hazards in your area? (Please reply only if you are representing a local, regional or national authority)
5. Are you aware of any specific measures or practices that are in place to tackle the problem of dust events (and the subsequent effect on energy, environment, water, health) and/or air pollution and/ or fire hazards in the greater area?
6. Are you aware of any relevant activities planned for the near future? Which parameters are currently being measured in your area? Would additional in-situ data help tackle the problem of air pollution fire hazard energy security and/or environmental degradation and/or poverty in your area?
7. What do you think is missing from the local population to be better prepared against forecasted dust events (and/or the subsequent effect on energy) and/or air pollution and/or fire hazards? (awareness raising, training, situational awareness, personalised technological solutions / ICT tools, targeted policies etc.)
8. How does the decision-making process of your Organisation to deal with dust storms (and the subsequent effect on energy, environment, water, health) and/or air pollution and/or fire hazards currently work? (Please reply only if you are representing a local or National authority)?

Questions addressed through an online survey (Mentimeter software):

1. Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/ see fit, so that you ultimately efficiently uptake the solutions proposed through the pilots of CiROCCO (answers only by those who will uptake the solutions, e.g. regularity authorities, university)? (*more than 1 replies possible*)
 - Seminars
 - Webinars
 - On-the-job training (e.g. hands-on, long-term support)
 - Workshops (dedicated synchronous events with defined skill-development outcomes)
 - Other (*empty space to write*)
2. Which modalities of tool documentation do you find preferable, to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CiROCCO solutions (answers only by those who will uptake the solutions)? (*more than 1 replies possible*)
 - Manual
 - Guidelines
 - Tutorial
 - Video
 - Other training material (*empty space to write*)

3.3. Exploration of potential Activities and Modalities for CD interventions

The potential CD activities range from physical to virtual interactive events, supporting activities, documents, videos or others, which will provide examples/ modalities that CiROCCO might adopt, according to the needs of each pilot and preferences of the involved communities.

Table 3: Capacity Development activities and modalities CiROCCO pilots will optionally adopt.

No#	Activity	Modality	Comments
1	General awareness event(s)	Interactive/synchronous workshops	
2	Technological (software and or hardware) training(s).	Seminars Webinars Hands-on training	Augmentation or addition to existing knowledge, datasets and technologies. Specific skill development.
3	Tools	Training materials Videos SOPs Guidelines Repositories	To support and empower ongoing learning before and/or after the rest of CD activities.
4	Assistance and advice	Regular/ systematic online networking Side-events Newsletters Webinars	Continued support beyond the lifetime of the CiROCCO (pilots) is critical to sustained product/solution adoption.
5	Long-term stewardship.	Web-presence maintenance technical support.	Beyond CiROCCO's lifetime.

Outputs of the online survey distributed during the interactive workshop in Cyprus and Serbia (Pilot 2 and 3, respectively), relevant to CD activities and modalities are shown below (Figure 3-6). As evident, webinars are preferred for Pilot 2, followed by seminars and hands-on training. Hands-on training and workshops are the most popular modes for CD in the case of Pilot 3. Videos seem the most popular means of activity, followed by guidelines for both pilots.

Which modalities of training activities would you prefer/ see fit, so that you ultimately efficiently uptake the solutions proposed? (not all)

Figure 3: Online survey results (Question 1) from the stakeholder workshop in Cyprus (Pilot 2). Note: The (one) response 'Other' refers to a Mobile app.

Which modalities of tool documentation you find preferable, so as to empower ongoing learning and efficient uptake of CiROCCO solutions (not all)

Figure 4: Online survey results (Question 2) from the stakeholder workshop in Cyprus (Pilot 2). Note: The (one) response 'Other' refers to technological support.

In your opinion, which models of training/training activities do you consider appropriate, in order to eventually effectively adopt the solutions proposed through the CiROCCO pilot (answer only by institutions and organizations that will adopt the solutions, e.g. competent authorities, university)?

Figure 5: as for Figure 3, but for Serbia (Pilot 3).

Which documentation models do you consider preferable, in order to enable continuous learning and efficient adoption of CiROCCO solutions (answers only those who will adopt the solutions)?

Figure 6: as for Figure 4, but for Serbia (Pilot 3).

3.4. Indicators to measure CD impact/ implementation

The definition of qualitative and quantitative indicators of CD progress toward outcomes and outputs is a good practice for a CD strategy. These indicators should map to the definitions of outcomes and outputs and be designed to measure progress against the conditions at project initiation (baseline) throughout the project lifetime. Table 4 maps indicative indicators to report on the (successful) CD implementation.

Table 4: Indicative qualitative and quantitative indicators to measure CD implementation (output) and impact (outcome) in the frame of CiROCCO.

No#	Indicator	Type	Level
1	The assessment results of the training and training providers have been positive.	Qualitative	Output
2	Do CD activity participants (individuals) transfer the gained knowledge to their departments?	Qualitative	Outcome
3	Do policymakers (or other end-users) use the CiROCCO tool for decision-making?	Qualitative	Outcome
4	How many citizens use the developed mobile app?	Quantitative	Outcome
5	Number of agencies adopting the developed tools/solutions.	Quantitative	Outcome
6	Number of communities or even individuals benefiting from the tool/product provision.	Quantitative	Outcome
7	Number of participants/institutions in the training.	Quantitative	Output
8	Number of new products, available through your activities	Quantitative	Output

(Source: Adapted from GEO users' guide)

The monitoring and evaluation of the above information gathered after the CD interventions during each pilot lifetime will reflect potential improvements in the ability of the CD interventions to achieve outcomes.

3.5. Knowledge transfer and capacity building plan

The four CD tools already described dictate the different phases of the knowledge transfer and capacity building plan of CiROCCO project (Figure 7). The plan proposed is comprised of 3 phases:

- Phase 1: Engagement with key stakeholders. Sections 3.1 and 3.2 provide the tools to this purpose, together with preliminary outcomes.
- Phase 2: Implementation of knowledge transfer activities. Section 3.3 provides the tools to this purpose. Each pilot should select the most appropriate intervention(s) for its nature/ desired impact. In particular, the (to be) developed training material will be delivered by dedicated partners (Table 2) based on their expertise for promotion of the wider project outreach in all participating countries and across EU and beyond, through the selected modalities of CD (Table 3).
- Phase 3: Monitoring and evaluation of CD activities. Section 3.4 provides potential indicators to be used for this purpose.

Figure 7: The knowledge transfer and capacity building plan of CiROCCO project.

4. CiROCCO case studies

The Capacity development plan and activity for each pilot of CiROCCO is a stand-alone case study that provides insight into the CD interventions and the way they have been designed, implemented and evaluated. In the next four sections, a short report on the four CD initiatives is provided, following the template provided by GEO. The report attempts to answer the following questions:

1. Which is the challenge of taking the CD initiative?
2. Which is the solution to address the scope?
3. Who are the key players involved and their roles?
4. What are the contributions of the parties to achieve impact?
5. What is planned/ has been done and what will be/are the tangible results?
6. What went well and what can be improved?
7. How can the achieved impact be expanded?

The final version of this deliverable (D5.4) will contain all the below sections updated, according to the implementation and evaluation of each CD plan.

4.1. CD for Pilot 1: Optimization of Solar Energy Management

Challenge. The exploitation of solar radiation and atmospheric measurements (incl. dust) and of solar energy potential forecasts by public and commercial investors on the Benban solar farm (Egypt).

Expected impact. Increased awareness of the role of the pilot measurements and forecasts on the exploitation of solar energy.

Stakeholders involved. CiROCCO side: CEDARE (leader), NOA, INTRA, EBOS, and ICCS will be involved with the role of ‘trainer’. Non-project side: The Egyptian M. of Electricity and Renewable Energy and other investors in the area are the ‘trainees’ in the CD procedure.

Main outcomes. The integration of the new atmospheric monitoring system and the optimized system to forecast solar energy potential into existing workflows applied in the solar farm area.

Concrete activities and outputs. At this phase, Activity No. 1 (Table 3) is scheduled for January 2024. Outputs will define additional CD activities in the future and as pilot activities proceed.

Evaluation, reflection, and lessons learned. To be assessed.

Up- or Out-scaling opportunities. To be assessed.

4.2. CD for Pilot 2: Adoption of an Early Warning System for Desert Dust Storms

Challenge. Frequent and severe desert dust storms affect Cyprus and by extension the Idalion Municipality area, which is already an area burdened by Particulate Matter (PM) concentrations.

Expected impact. Engagement of local authorities and citizens with the pilot products: atmospheric monitoring sensor network and EWS available through internet website and/or mobile application.

Stakeholders involved. Trainer side: UCY (leader), NOA, CEDARE, EBOS, INTRA, ICCS. Trainees: DIMOS, MOL, Ministry of Labour, Welfare and Social Insurance, local community.

Main outcomes. The integration of the new atmospheric monitoring system into the established monitoring networks and the use of the EWS by the local authorities.

Concrete activities and outputs. Activity No. 1 (Table 3) has been organised (October, 2023). The main outputs relevant to capacity development according to the responses to the questionnaire of the first Stakeholders Workshop, are:

- i. 76% out of a total of 21 participants, consider DDS an extremely or important problem in their area.
- ii. Of those who responded, 45% believe that the Governmental Bodies are the primary bodies responsible for addressing the issue of DDS events, in a question with many possible responses.
- iii. 52.4% of the participants responded that more in-situ data helps address the DDS issue in their area, while 47.6% of interviewees submitted no response at all, presumably because of the limited knowledge they possessed on the topic.
- iv. Due to the limited information, the participants recommended that more targeted information campaigns and trainings be carried out for the general population on issues of adaptation to the problem.

Evaluation, reflection, and lessons learned. To be assessed.

Up- or Out-scaling opportunities. Assuming that the EWS, which utilises CIROCCO's sensing node system, works successfully and reliably, it can be adopted by the competent authorities at the national level. In the future, the case of EWS being outscaled in Mediterranean areas affected by DDS will be investigated.

4.3. CD for Pilot 3: Sustainability of the new Atmospheric Monitoring System

Challenge. Micro-climate and air pollution monitoring are important for the sustainable management of Deliblato Sands (Serbia).

Expected impact. Operational use of the CiROCCO's network and observations by the responsible authorities and/or local governments of neighbouring cities.

Stakeholders involved. Project side: VSUME (leader), INO, EBOS, INTRA, ICCS. Others: local authorities.

Main outcomes. The capacity to sustain the new air monitoring network.

Concrete activities and outputs. Activity No. 1 (Table 3) has been realized (December, 2023). The collected material will be assessed by the pilot leader in due time.

Evaluation, reflection, and lessons learned. To be assessed.

Up- or Out-scaling opportunities. To be assessed.

4.4. CD for Pilot 4: Understanding the role of atmospheric dust on ecosystem and groundwater quality

Challenge. Understanding how desert atmospheric dust intrusions affect the ecosystem and groundwater quality in coastal drylands with heavily exploited aquifers (southern Spain).

Expected impact. Engagement of local authorities with the pilot products: atmospheric monitoring sensor network.

Stakeholders involved. Project side: CSIC (leader), INO, EBOS, INTRA, ICCS. Trainees: Local and regional water, land, air quality and health agencies, agricultural and solar energy companies, and the local community.

Main outcomes. The capacity to sustain the new air monitoring network.

Concrete activities and outputs. At this phase, Activity No. 1 is scheduled for the first quarter of 2024 after stakeholders are integrated. Outputs will define additional CD activities in the future and as pilot activities proceed.

Evaluation, reflection, and lessons learned. To be assessed.

Up- or Out-scaling opportunities. To be assessed.

5. Liaison activities in the frame of T5.2 - Policy Outreach on Hard-to-reach Areas

In the frame of CiROCCO development and outcomes, policy interventions are/will be pursued, through Liaison activities with decision-makers at different levels and scales. The objectives of this activity are given below:

1. Disseminate the outcomes of the proposed new policies and how they will affect the environmental protection status.
2. Disseminate the developed solutions and how they could enhance the geographical coverage of in-situ environmental observations for competitive sustainability. In particular, cultivate acceptance and support the future role of unauthorized networks of sensors (which is growing both in cities but also in unrepresented areas).
3. Create a set of practical recommendations that will give support to policy initiatives, that are currently being designed under the Green Deal and Digital Age, the Copernicus Expansion Missions and the European strategy for data.
4. Consolidation of training material experiences along with challenges faced during the project execution (WP3, WP4).
5. Interact with GEO CD-WG: CD training activities will be aligned to and be proposed as part of the activities of CD-WG (concretely realizing the Canberra Declaration point 17, with emphasis on the Global South).
6. Contribute to and support actions of the Science Policy Forum, IUCN Forum, World Environmental Hubs, Earth Observation Sentinel Hub, and more.

Below, the realized Liaison activities are provided in chronological order, demonstrating their link(s) to the above goals (Table 5). The list will be continuously updated and presented in D5.4 (final).

Table 5: Liaison activities in the frame of CiROCCO

No#	Contacted Organization	CiROCCO partner	Date	Place	Scope*
1	GEO (Ernest Acheampong, Coordinator of the Capacity Development Working Group)	NOA (Eleni Athanasopoulou and Evangelos Gerasopoulos)	26/04/2023	remote	5, 2
2	Leaders of Research Infrastructures	NOA (Evangelos Gerasopoulos)	8-10/5/2023	Helsinki	2
3	GEO (Ernest Acheampong, Coordinator of the Capacity Development Working Group)	NOA (Evangelos Gerasopoulos)	GEO Symposium, 13-14/06/2023	Geneve	5, 2
4	GEO (Ernest Acheampong, Coordinator of the Capacity Development Working Group)	NOA (Eleni Athanasopoulou and Evangelos Gerasopoulos)	3/07/2023	remote	5
5	GEO (Ernest Acheampong, Coordinator of the Capacity Development Working Group)	NOA (Eleni Athanasopoulou)	9/11/2023	GEO week, Cape Town	5

*No of Goal from the above list

6. Conclusions

This document (D5.3, initial version) defines the capacity development (CD) strategy of the CiROCCO project and describes all preparatory actions for the implementation of CD in the frame of each of the four pilot cases/areas. In parallel, it demonstrates the scope of Liaison activities, as well as a short summary of those performed so far.

In particular, the CD strategy is aligned with the principles of a) engagement with key players (here, the pilot leaders), which has already taken place with their main results presented inline. In addition, b) CD demands an exploration of potential activities and modalities for CD interventions. To this end, c) the interaction with stakeholders is essential and has already started for 3 out of the 4 pilots. The first feedback has identified different types of favourite interventions per pilot (webinars and on-the-job training), while videos (and guidelines) are the most (2nd most) favourable supportive/documentation tools for CD for both pilots who already provided feedback (pilot 2 and 3). At the later stages of CD implementation, d) the indicators -already proposed in this document- will help measure CD impact/implementation.

Each pilot is a unique case study concerning the design, development, implementation and evaluation of CD interventions; thus 4 individual templates have been created and will be finalized in the second version of this document (D5.4, final version). The systematic interaction of CiROCCO and GEO in the field of CD has been established towards an exchange of experience and good practices.

7. References

1. *Group of Earth Observations (GEO), (2022). User guide on good practices for designing, implementing, and evaluating capacity development interventions. Example of Journal, 50-62.*
2. *United Nations Development Group, UNDAF COMPANION GUIDANCE: CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT, <https://unsdg.un.org/sites/default/files/UNDG-UNDAF-Companion-Pieces-8-Capacity-Development.pdf>*